

The Effect of Quality of Service and Price on Consumer Satisfaction at Honda Workshop AHASS 07723 Tajur Raya Bogor

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze and identify the effect of service quality and price both simultaneously and partially on customer satisfaction at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop. The total sample of all consumers is 100 people. The questionnaire was tested with validity tests, reliability tests, and also classic assumption tests. The results of these tests are valid, reliable, and can be used for regression data. The analytical method used in this study is a descriptive and verification method with a quantitative approach. The results showed that the variables of service quality and price both simultaneously and partially had a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the Honda Workshop AHASS 07723 Tajur. The test results for the coefficient of determination (R Square) are 47.8% while the remaining is 52.2%. The relationship between service quality and price is very strong with a correlation coefficient of 0.691.

INTRODUCTION

The large number of Indonesian people is a promising market share for all industries, especially the automotive and motorcycle industries. Motorcycle brands on the Indonesian motorcycle market generally originate from Japan, such as Honda, Yamaha, Suzuki and Kawasaki. Motorcycles are a means of transportation that have an important role in society, both individuals and companies.

This is because motorbikes have a flexibility value in reaching narrow spaces (narrow roads) that cannot be reached by large vehicles such as cars. The city of Bogor is one of the cities in West Java which is growing rapidly and has a good level of economic growth, so that many automotive companies are expanding their business in Bogor City. The following is a list of the names of motorcycle repair shops:

Table 1. Motorcycle Service Companies in Bogor City in 2021

No	Company name	Motorcycle Brand	Business Activity
1	Honda AHASS 07723	Honda	Service and Spare Parts
2	Mitra Fajar Ciawi	Honda	Service and Spare Parts
3	PT Setia Anugerah Motor	Honda	Sales, Service and Parts
4	Yamaha Arista Tajur	Yamaha	Sales, Service and Parts
5	Yamaha Primautama	Yamaha	Sales, Service and Parts
6	Arista Megatama Tajur	Yamaha	Sales, Service and Parts
7	Kawasaki Motorave Tajur	Kawasaki	Sales, Service and Parts

Source: Author Processed Data, 2021

Based on the table, it explains the names of motorbike service companies in Bogor City. With so many companies in the same field, the competition is getting tougher. Intense competition among motorcycle service companies encourages companies to develop the right strategy so that the industry can win the competition. One strategy to win the competition is to provide satisfaction to consumers (Kotler and Keller 2013:140).

Honda AHASS 07723 is an official repair shop in the city of Bogor. Honda Workshop AHASS 07723 Tajur Raya Bogor was established in 2005. Its business activities include servicing motorbikes for both maintenance and repair of engines and sales of spare parts. The AHASS 07723 Honda Workshop uses standard equipment, provides genuine Honda spare parts as well as various information on performing periodic servicing, not infrequently the Honda AHASS 07723 Workshop does promos for reducing service prices and providing services in the form of Service At Home.

Based on the total number of service users at official repair shops in 2021, there are 10,532 consumers. The highest number of consumers servicing motorbikes in December reached 1060 people with a target percentage of 101% of the target customer visit of 1054 people, this is because it coincides with the New Year's holiday when many people repair motorized vehicles and also companies provide various promos, so many consumers are interested in servicing their vehicles at the Official Honda AHASS 07723 workshop.

Consumer satisfaction to use certain services is a complex process. Many things are considered by consumers to use these services. One of the consumer considerations is to look at the quality of the services provided and compare

prices with each other's companies, with the aim of getting the results they expect.

Based on the description of the background of the problem, the expected goals in this study are as follows:

1. To find out consumer responses regarding service quality, price and customer satisfaction at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur Raya Bogor workshop.
2. To analyze service quality and price simultaneously on customer satisfaction at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur Raya Bogor workshop.
3. To analyze service quality and price partially on customer satisfaction at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur Raya Bogor workshop.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Marketing Management

Marketing management is a combination of several interrelated activities to find out consumer needs through creating, offering and exchanging products and services of value and developing promotions, distribution, services and prices so that consumer needs and wants can be properly satisfied (Sudaryono, 2016: 42).

Service quality

Service quality is the totality of the characteristics of goods and services that show their ability to satisfy consumer needs, both obvious and hidden (Kotler, 2014: 35). The indicators of service quality in this study according to Kotler and Keller (2016: 284) are as follows: Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy.

Price

Price is the money demanded for goods and services, or the amount that consumers exchange for the use and possession of goods and services. (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016:65). The price indicators in this study according to Kotler and Armstrong (2016: 52) are as follows: Price affordability, price compatibility with quality, price compatibility with benefits, price competitiveness.

Consumer Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction is the extent to which the perceived performance of a product or service is in line with expectations, namely the extent to which the perceived ability of a product or service fulfills dreams (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016: 39). The indicators of consumer satisfaction in this study according to Tjiptono (2014: 101) are as follows: Conformity of expectations, Interest in visiting, Willingness to recommend.

Figure 1. Thinking Framework

Research Resign

Descriptive research is a method that can be used to draw larger conclusions (Sugiyono, 2014: 20). On the other hand, for Sugiyono, verification is research through evidence to test the assumptions of descriptive research by using statistical calculations to find out whether assumptions are accepted or rejected. (2014: 23).

The population based on the number of customers at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur Raya Bogor workshop in 2021 is 10,532 people. To determine which respondents were used as samples, a sample of 100 people was obtained. The sample size of consumers in each section is carried out by purposive sampling.

The type of research data is quantitative. According to Sugiyono (2019: 14), quantitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of positivism that studies specific populations or samples, uses research tools in data collection, analyzes data that is quantitative or statistical in nature, and the goal is to test predetermined hypotheses. According to (Juliandi & Manarung, 2014, p. 65), Primary Data is raw data taken by researchers or data that has never existed before from primary sources that are useful for research purposes. While secondary data, namely data excerpts by researchers from pre-existing data for the benefit of their research.

METHODS

The purpose of the validity test as explained by Sugiyono (2014: 121) is to find out how accurately the instrument measures the construct of interest. The validity test was tried on 30 respondents. The research results prove that all service quality indicator values (X₁), price (X₂) and customer satisfaction (Y) are declared valid because the r-number is greater than 0.3.

After the measuring instrument is considered valid, the tool is tested for reliability. According to (Sugiyono, 2014: 121), the reliability test is the result of measurements on the same subject, so that the information obtained is the same. The device is considered reliable if the reliability aspect is at least 0.6. The results of the reliability test proved that in this study all parts of the indicators X1, X2 and Y were claimed to be reliable because the Cronbach's alpha number was > 0.6 .

Classic Assumption Test

The classic hypothesis test tries the assumption of linear regression, which aims to avoid bias in the analysis of data and errors in the details of the form used. (Rochaety, Tresnati, & Latief, 2019, p. 176). The test uses classical assumptions, namely normality, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity.

1. Normality Test

The results of the normality test using the normal probability path prove that a straight line is a diagonal line and the point following the diagonal line is the data of this research. Looking at the normal probability plot plot, it appears that the information is distributed along the line and follows the diagonal line, so the shape fulfills the assumption of normality. The following is a normality test image using a probability plot graph:

Figure 2. Normal Probability Plots
Source: Processed data, 2022

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test yielded statistically significant findings, indicating that the data followed a normal distribution. The two-sided Asymptotic Significance value of 0.200 indicates that the significance level is > 0.05 . This table is a normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method.

Table 2. Normality Test Results

<i>One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test</i>		
		<i>Unstandardized Residual</i>
<i>N</i>		100
<i>Normal Parameters^{a,b}</i>	<i>Mean</i>	.0000000
	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	2.13922031
<i>Most Extreme Differences</i>	<i>Absolute</i>	.065
	<i>Positive</i>	.065
	<i>Negative</i>	-.033
<i>Test Statistic</i>		.065
<i>Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)</i>		.200 ^{c,d}

Source: Processed data, 2022

2. Muticollarity Test

Free Multicollinearity tolerance > 0.1 and VIF < 10. The results show tolerance X1 0.389 and X2 0.389 meaning > 0.1. Whereas VIF values X1 2.570 and X2 2.570 mean <10, so this study is free from multicollinearity.

3. Heteroscedasticity Test

The results of the heteroscedasticity test prove that the points are spread irregularly and are less than 0 on Y. It is concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in this form of regression, allowing the model in this study to take into account any variable. Here's the scatterplot graph:

Figure 3. Scatterplot Graph

Source: Processed data, 2022

Data Analysis Methods

The Likert scale was used in the study. Sugiyono (2019: 168), cites the Likert scale as a tool for measuring people's reactions, perspectives, and opinions after an event. Variables measured by Likert ratios can be replaced with variable indicators. The indicator then becomes a reference in making instrument parts, which can be in the form of statements or problems. The following is a Likert scale table:

Table 3. Likert Scale

Response	Score
Strongly Agree	5
Agree	4
Quite Agree	3
Don't Agree	2
Totally Disagree	1

Source: Sugiyono (2019)

Multiple regression analysis studies evaluate how an event influences individual and group behaviors, perspectives, and preconceived notions. Variables measured by Likert ratios can be replaced with elastic indicators. These indicators then become a reference in making instrument parts, which can be in the form of statements or questions.

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Then, the multiple correlation is a value that reports the direction and strength of the bond between 2 independent variables at once or with more than one dependent variable. (Sugiyono, 2016, p. 286). To see the magnitude of the contribution of the variables X_1 and X_2 with the coefficient of determination calculated in the formula:

$$KD = r^2 \times 100\%$$

Hypothesis Test

F-test to simultaneously test the significance of the equation to identify the effect of the independent variables jointly on the dependent variable. The formulation of the hypothesis used is:

- 1) $H_0: \beta_i \leq 0$, There is no statistically significant correlation between service quality and price and consumer satisfaction.
- 2) $H_a: \beta_i > 0$, consumers are more satisfied when they receive high-quality services at reasonable prices.

The F test formula is:

$$F = \frac{\frac{R^2}{K}}{(1 - R^2)(n - K - 1)}$$

After obtaining the results of the F-test calculation, it is then determined by the F-test formulation criteria:

- 1.) If F count is more < F table, then H_0 is allowed and H_a is rejected up to p 0.05, which indicates that there is no positive and significant effect of service quality and price on customer satisfaction.
- 2.) Service quality and price have a positive and substantial effect on customer satisfaction if Fcount > Ftable and H_0 is rejected by = 0.05 but H_a is accepted.

The t-test, on the other hand, is a partial significance test that looks at whether X has an impact or not on Y. In terms of hypothesis formulation:

- 1) X_1 against Y
 - a) $H_0: \beta_i \leq 0$, service quality does not have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.

- b) Ha1: $\beta_i > 0$, service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.
- 2) X2 on Y
- a) Ho2: $\beta_i \leq 0$, price does not have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.
 - b) Ha2: $\beta_i > 0$, price has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

To see whether the independent variables are significant, namely service quality and price in a partial (individual) way on consumer satisfaction.

$$t = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

The criteria for the formulation of the t test are:

- 1) For service quality (X1), if t count is lower or the same on t table ($t \text{ count} \leq t \text{ table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ until Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected, that is service quality does not have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction, while if tcount is wider than ttable ($t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ until Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected, so service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.
- 2) For price (X2), if t count is lower or the same on t table ($t \text{ count} \leq t \text{ table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ until Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected, so the price does not have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction, meanwhile if t count wider than ttable ($t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$) at $\alpha = 0.05$ until Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected, so that price has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

RESULTS

Consumer Characteristics

The customer characteristics of Honda Workshop AHASS 07723 Tajur are the sample, namely predominantly male, aged 27-33 years, privately employed, income Rp. 4,100,000 - Rp. 5,000,000.

Consumer Responses to Service Quality Variables (X1), Price (X2), and Consumer Satisfaction (Y)

The results of service quality recapitulation have an average value of 3.86 in a good interpretation. This states that service quality is an important aspect to meet consumer satisfaction. In accordance with the opinion (Kotler, 2014: 35), states that the quality of services, namely the totality of the characteristics of objects and services, proves their ability to satisfy consumer desires. The highest score of 3.97 with a good interpretation is the statement that the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop provides safe waiting room facilities and has professional mechanics. This is evidenced by the consumer's assessment of the facilities provided and the company has an internal program in the form of training or certification for its employees. Apart from improving soft skills and hard skills, training like this helps workers provide better services that meet or exceed consumer expectations. So it can be concluded that the quality of service

is largely influenced by comfortable waiting room facilities and professional mechanics.

The results of the recapitulation of consumer responses regarding prices have an average rating of 3.58 including the affordable category. This is if the price becomes an important aspect to determine consumer satisfaction. In accordance with the opinion (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016: 65), states that money is burdened for goods and services, or numbers replaced by customers for the benefits of using and owning objects and services. The highest value of 3.74 is included in the affordable category, which is a statement according to the results that consumers want. This is evidenced by the way Honda Workshop AHASS 07723 Tajur provides good quality services for maintaining and repairing motorcycle vehicles. So it can be concluded that prices are largely influenced by the results desired by consumers.

The results of the recapitulation of consumer responses regarding consumer satisfaction have an average rating of 3.79 including the satisfied category. The highest score is 3.95, namely on the service indicator meeting consumer needs. It is proven that the services provided by the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop meet consumer needs.

Multiple Regression Analysis

The regression equation with the estimated model is obtained in the regression analysis, namely:

$$Y = 1,839 + 0,277 X_1 + 0,244 X_2 + \epsilon$$

Each of these variables is explained, namely:

- 1) The constant value obtained is 1.839, meaning that when X_1 and $X_2 = 0$, Y Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop is positive.
- 2) The regression coefficient of service quality (X_1) is positive (0.277) which means that every time a level of service quality occurs (X_1) it is followed by an increase in customer satisfaction (Y) at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop on the assumption that X_2 is fixed.
- 3) The regression coefficient X_2 has a positive value (0.244) meaning that the better the assessment regarding the price (X_2) the increase in Y at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop on the assumption that the service quality variable (X_1) is fixed.

Tabel 4. Multiple Correlation Calculation Results
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Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.691 ^a	.478	.467	3.460

Source: Processed data, 2022

The statistical calculation is known so that the R value or relationship is equal to 0.691 which proves the relationship or bond from X_1 and X_2 and the limited variable is customer happiness (Y) which has a strong correlation (0.600 - 0.800) and is positive Sugiyono (2019: 267). So it can be concluded that the

better the value of variable X, the higher the value of variable Y and vice versa. The better the quality of service (X1) and price (X2) so that it will directly result in increasing consumer satisfaction (Y).

Coefficient of Determination (R Square)

Based on the chart, the results obtained are R-squared of 0.478 or 47.8%. This proves that the effect of service quality and price variables on customer satisfaction at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop is 47.8%, the remaining 52.2% is influenced by elasticity outside the scope of this study such as location, promotion, facilities and atmosphere (Tjiptono and Gregorius , 2016: 295).

Simultaneous Regression Model Testing

To test the statistical hypothesis, the F test statistic is used:

Table 5. Simultaneous Regression Coefficient Test Results

Model	Sum Of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1062.945	2	531.472	44.373	.000 ^b
Residual	1161.805	97	11.977		
Total	2224.750	99			

Source: Processed data, 2022

Based on this chart, we get Fcount of 44,373, while Ftable must be calculated using a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and the independence part ($df = n-k$) or $100-2-1 = 97$. So looking at the independence part, we get the Ftable value, namely 3.090 $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($44.373 > 3.090$) and has a significant number of $0.000 < 0.05$ so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is obtained which means service quality (X1) and price (X2) simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the workshop Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur.

Partial Regression Model Testing

The t test was carried out how X1 and X2 partially affect Y at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop, so it can be seen in table 4.23 the tcount value and the significant figures of each independent variable. While the ttable number for $\alpha = 0.05$ degrees of freedom $n-k-1$ is 1.661, the result is.

Table 6. T Test Results

Coefficients ^a			
	Model	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.792	.430
	Kualitas Pelayanan	3.464	.001
	Harga	2.757	.007

Source: Processed data, 2022

1. The Influence of Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction at Honda Workshop AHASS 07723 Tajur

Service quality (X1) with a tcount of 3.464 is greater than the ttable value of 1.661 ($3.464 > 1.661$) and a significant value of $0.001 < 0.05$. H_{a1} is accepted and H_{o1} is rejected, which means that the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop benefits from the X1 in several ways. This is the same as the results

of research by Henny Armaniah (2019) and Muhamad Jumhari (2022), if service quality has a sizable beneficial effect on the level of satisfaction felt by corporate clients. The one-sided test for the service quality variable in the picture:

Figure 4. Quality of Service Variable t-test results (X1)

Source: Processed data, 2022

2. The Influence of Price on Consumer Satisfaction at Honda Workshop AHASS 07723 Tajur

Price (X2) with a tcount of 2.757 is greater than the ttable value of 1.661 ($2.757 > 1.661$) and a significant value of 0.007 is smaller than 0.5 ($0.007 > 0.05$). So thus H_{a2} is accepted and H_{o2} is rejected, meaning that partially X2 has a positive and significant effect on Y at the Honda AHASS workshop 07723 Tajur. According to research by Roza Maya Sari and Efry Kurnia (2018) and Abdul Gofur (2019), explaining that price has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. The one-sided test for the following image price variable:

Figure 5. Price variable t test (X2)

Source: Processed data, 2022

From the test results, a partial summary of the test was made, namely the service quality variable (X1) and price (X2), namely:

Table 7. Recapitulation of Partial Tests

No	Variable	t _{count}	t _{table}	Sig	A	Decision	Conclusion
1	Service Quality	3,464	1,661	0,001	0,05	Ha ₁ Accepted	Service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.
2	Price	2,757	1,661	0,007	0,05	Ha ₂ Accepted	Price has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

Source: Processed data, 2022

All of these variables have tcount values that exceed ttable values, proving this. X1 is the dominant variable affecting Y. This can be proven through the magnitude of the Standardized Corfficient Beta value for the service quality variable (X1) which is as much as 0.407 where this value is the largest value compared to the Standardized Effective Beta value for the price variable (X2) of 0.324.

DISCUSSION

The regression coefficient is a number that shows the magnitude of the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. Usually the influence of each of these variables can be explained as follows:

1. The constant value obtained is 1.839, which means that when service quality (X1) and price (X2) = 0, consumer satisfaction (Y) at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop is positive.
2. The service quality regression coefficient (X1) is positive (0.277), which means that every time there is an increase in service quality (X1), it will be followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction (Y) at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop with the assumption that the price variable (X2) is constant. The Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop provides good quality service and if the service quality is good then consumers will feel satisfied with the services provided by the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop.
3. The price regression coefficient (X2) is positive (0.244), which means that the better the assessment regarding price (X2), the greater the consumer satisfaction (Y) at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop with the assumption that the service quality variable (X1) is constant. Competitive prices make consumers more confident in the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on research results and hypothesis testing regarding the effect of service quality and price on customer satisfaction at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop, the conclusions obtained are:

1. Consumer response to service quality and price to consumer satisfaction at Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur Workshop, concluded if:
 - a) The quality of service (X1) at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop is generally good.
 - b) The price (X2) at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop is considered affordable.
 - c) The level of consumer satisfaction (Y) of the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop is classified as satisfied.
2. At the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop, X1 and X2 have a positive and statistically significant effect on Y simultaneously (F Test).
3. Partial hypothesis testing (t test) shows that X1 and X2 have a positive and statistically significant effect on Y at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop.

FURTHER STUDY

Suggestions from research are:

1. Based on consumer responses regarding service quality, namely employees provide individual attention to consumers. Therefore, it is necessary to increase employee empathy towards consumers with the aim of making consumers feel well cared for. In this way, consumers will decide to carry out maintenance and repairs on their motorbikes again at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop.
2. Consumer responses to prices at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop, namely that the price of the service is in accordance with the consumer's financial condition. This requires price adjustments to be carried out by the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop with the aim of being in line with consumer expectations and being able to meet company targets. That way, consumers will decide to carry out maintenance and repairs on their motorbikes at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop.
3. Consumer responses to customer satisfaction at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur repair shop, namely making the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur repair shop the first choice, however, there needs to be an increase in the quality of services provided by the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur repair shop with the aim of making consumers feel satisfied and have a growing sense of interest Visit the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop again to carry out maintenance and repairs on your motorbike at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop.
4. For future researchers, this research will serve as a benchmark and reference. Future researchers are advised to look for variables that influence customer satisfaction at the Honda AHASS 07723 Tajur workshop, apart from service quality and price, so that they can get more varied results and influence customer satisfaction to get a greater significant value.

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